

COMPARISON OF NORMAL AND PATHOLOGICAL ERUPTION OF DECIDUOUS TEETH IN CHILDREN

¹Eshimova S.T., ²Alimdjanova M.S., ³Bozorboyev A.O.

^{1,2}Nursing Academy

^{1,3}Tashkent State Dental Institute

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14030349>

Abstract. *This article identifies early and late eruption patterns of deciduous teeth in children based on a multifactorial analysis. These conditions were observed in preschool-aged children with dental caries and its complications, as well as in school-aged children due to insufficient space in the jaws for permanent teeth. A total of 23 children (11 girls - 47.8%, 12 boys - 52.2%) were examined. The examination results showed that 13 children (56.5%) had early and late eruption of deciduous teeth, while 10 children (43.5%) exhibited normal eruption patterns. Pathological conditions were identified in 4 children (30.9%) due to calcium deficiency, in 3 children (23%) - due to vitamin D deficiency, and in 6 children (46.1%) - due to deficiencies in both calcium and vitamin D. Additionally, other risk factors contributing to pathology were noted, including chronic illnesses in the mother, poor maternal habits, illnesses during pregnancy, toxicosis in the second half of pregnancy, and illnesses during the first year of the child's life. To prevent and detect pathologies early, it is necessary for pregnant women to be under the supervision of doctors during their pregnancy, and for the child to be monitored by a pediatrician and a pediatric dentist from birth. It is also essential to ensure that clinical and laboratory examinations are conducted.*

Keywords: *hypersalivation, obesity, rickets, infectious diseases, natural nutrition, artificial feeding, chronic diseases.*

Introduction: The process of the tooth germ's placement and development within the jaw, as well as its vertical movement until the tooth emerges and a crown appears in the oral cavity. Since the eruption of primary teeth is a physiological process, it does not occur alongside any general or local pathological manifestations. However, in some children, the eruption of primary teeth may be accompanied by a rise in body temperature, refusal to eat, and dyspeptic symptoms. Increased salivation is noted in the child, along with hyperemia in the oral cavity and localized swelling of the gums in the area of the tooth projection. The early or late eruption of teeth depends on primary and secondary factors that can lead to pathology. Observations revealed that in 10 children, the timing of tooth eruption was normal, while 4 children experienced early eruption of primary teeth, and 9 children exhibited delayed eruption.

Purpose of the study: To identify early and late eruption of primary teeth in children based on multifactorial analysis, as well as to assess the relationship between the causes of the pathology and clinical-laboratory diagnoses in order to evaluate the early and late eruption of primary teeth.

Research Materials and Methods: The study was conducted at the Department of Pediatric Maxillofacial Surgery of Tashkent State Dental Institute. Clinical examinations were performed on 7 preschool-aged children suffering from odontogenic inflammatory diseases due to early eruption of primary teeth and poor oral hygiene. Additionally, caries treatment and oral cavity sanitation were carried out on 16 children at a private clinic.

The early eruption of teeth occurred in 4 children (17.4%) at the age of 3-5 months after birth. Late eruption of teeth was observed in 9 children (39.1%) at the age of 10-12 months after birth. Normal eruption of teeth was noted in 10 children (43.5%) at the age of 6-8 months.

table 1.

The timing of the emergence of primary teeth is presented in the following

Teeth	The beginning of mineralization	Completion of enamel formation	teething	Completion of root formation	The beginning of root resorption
1	4-months-old pregnancy	4 months old	6 to 8 months old	1,5 to 2 years old	4 years old
2	4-to-5-month-old pregnancy	5 months old	8 to 10 months old	1,5 to 2 years old	5 years old
3	5-month-old pregnancy	9 months old	16 to 20 months old	4 to 5 years old	8 years old
4	5-month-old pregnancy	6 months old	12 to 16 months old	2,5 to 3,5 years old	6 years old
5	6-month-old pregnancy	10 to 12 months old	20 to 30 months old	3 to 4 years old	7 years old

The condition of children with observed pathologies and the development of the dental system were assessed based on objective, radiological, and caries progression indicators, as well as the identification of caries prevalence and clinical-laboratory parameters. The examinations focused on objective signs that assist in the early detection of diseases, such as excessive sweating in the child, hair loss at the back of the head, the disproportionate timing of tooth eruption relative to age, and the presence of enamel demineralization and discoloration of teeth in the oral cavity, along with attention to caries involvement.

Results: In our examinations, early tooth eruption was observed in 4 children (17.4%). Delayed tooth eruption was noted in 9 children (39.1%), while 10 children (43.5%) exhibited normal timing of tooth eruption. Among the children, 4 (30.9%) showed signs of calcium deficiency, 3 (23%) had vitamin D₃ deficiency, and 5 (46.1%) experienced deficiencies in both calcium and vitamin D₃. Early eruption of primary teeth and the influence of adverse factors on dental tissues negatively affect tooth resilience. When teeth erupt at 3 months of age, the structural immaturity, insufficient mineralization of hard tissues, and lack of proper hygiene support can lead to early carious damage of primary teeth. Particular attention should be given to prematurely erupted temporary teeth during the prenatal period. This phenomenon often occurs with the lower central incisors and, less frequently, with the upper central incisors. The structure of these prematurely erupted teeth is typically defective, and their roots are not yet fully formed. The presence of such temporary teeth can lead to complications for both the mother and the child. During feeding, these teeth can damage the mammary gland, which often results in mastitis. These

teeth should be removed shortly after birth. Currently, there is no widely accepted theory regarding the causes of early eruption. **Delayed Eruption of Primary Teeth:** In normally developing children, the eruption of primary teeth occurs within a median timeframe. A significant delay in tooth eruption may indicate a disruption in the child's physical development, the presence of any metabolic disorders, or an underlying medical condition. In practically healthy children, lower central incisors appear in 3.25% of cases after one year. Anamnesis indicates that the delay in the eruption of primary teeth is often characteristic of one of the child's parents. The data obtained confirms that the process of primary tooth eruption in children is influenced by genetic factors. **Analysis of Results:** The eruption of primary teeth is a physiological process that usually occurs without any accompanying general or local pathological manifestations. However, in some children, the eruption of primary teeth is associated with a rise in body temperature, refusal to eat, and dyspeptic symptoms indicating a general state of disturbance. The child may be restless and have difficulty sleeping. Increased salivation is noted, along with hyperemia in the oral cavity and localized swelling of the gums at the projection of the teeth. Many factors influence the eruption of primary teeth. Some researchers attribute the primary role to genotype, but the influence of environmental factors cannot be dismissed. The literature does not provide a clear answer regarding the sexual characteristics of primary tooth eruption. Nevertheless, most authors believe that there is no gender difference. There is information in the literature about the eruption process of primary teeth in children with a severe prenatal history. A direct relationship exists between the degree of prematurity of the child and the timing of primary tooth eruption. It has also been established that diseases occurring during the neonatal period affect the process of primary tooth eruption. Thus, in healthy preterm infants, the timing of primary tooth eruption corresponds with that of healthy, full-term infants. In premature infants, the eruption of teeth (due to intracranial birth trauma, infectious and inflammatory diseases) begins later (at 11-12 months and after one year) and is related to the severity of the illness. When studying the characteristics of primary tooth eruption in premature infants, it was found that in 61% of cases, the eruption of the first teeth occurs at 8 months or later. The onset of tooth eruption is influenced by genetic factors, the duration of breastfeeding, and the health status of the mother during pregnancy and the newborn period, making this the leading factor of the antenatal period. As the duration of primary tooth formation increases, the correlation between adverse factors and the onset of eruption decreases. The period of pregnancy also affects the eruption of primary teeth. Metabolic changes are more pronounced with pregnancy toxemia. In a study of children under three years old whose mothers suffered from pregnancy toxemia, it was found that the timing of temporary tooth eruption was approximately doubled. The health of the mother has a direct impact on tooth eruption. Additionally, deviations in the eruption of primary teeth indicate a slowdown in intermandibular mineralization due to negative factors during pregnancy. In 37.39% of the cases, this condition was identified. The delayed eruption of primary teeth was observed in 27.74% of the cases. Along with the disruption of timing, changes in the pairing and sequence of primary teeth eruption were noted. Delayed eruption of primary teeth was recorded in children born to mothers with mitral valve defects.

In children whose mothers took metabolic medications during pregnancy, the average time for the eruption of the first primary tooth was 6-8 months. In the group of children whose mothers did not take these medications, this indicator was 7-8 months.

When analyzing the relationship between the state of the child's oral cavity and the health level of the mother during pregnancy, it was found that there was a strong correlation between the timing of primary tooth eruption in children and the total calcium content in the saliva of women at the beginning and end of pregnancy, indicating that a higher amount of calcium in saliva was observed. Conclusion: To determine the early or delayed eruption of teeth, it is essential to monitor the mother's pregnancy period and conduct medical examinations for both the mother and child after delivery. Observing the processes involved, implementing preventive measures, and prescribing vitamin D₃, calcium, and anti-anemia medications for both the mother and child is crucial. If objective signs indicating a deficiency of vitamin D₃ or calcium appear, laboratory tests (such as complete blood count and biochemical blood analysis) should be conducted. To prevent infectious and chronic diseases, the mother should avoid contact with individuals who have infectious diseases during pregnancy and in the early stages of the child's life. A diet rich in proteins, minerals, and vitamins should be followed. Additionally, significant attention must be paid to oral hygiene.

REFERENCES

1. Авраамова, О.Г. Влияние профилактических мероприятий на созревание эмали зубов у детей (обзор литературы) / О.Г. Авраамова, А.Р. Заборская // *Стоматология детского возраста и профилактика*. – 2015. – № 4. – С. 3–7.
2. Артеменко, В.В. Влияние социально-экономических характеристик семьи на здоровье детей / В.В. Артеменко // *Проблемы развития территории*. – 2009. – № 2 (48). – С. 68–76.
3. Бароева, А.Р. Особенности патогенеза и профилактики раннего детского кариеса / А.Р. Бароева, С.Ч. Мамиева // *Современные вопросы биомедицины*. – 2022. – Т. 6, № 1. DOI: 10.51871/2588-0500_2022_06_01_1
4. Вагапова, Д.А. Применение кейсов в социальной работе с семьями различных типов / Д.А. Вагапова, С.Н. Испулова // *Социальная политика и социальное партнерство*. – 2021. – № 1. – С. 63–74.
5. Воронин, Г.Л. Монородительские семьи: их типы и социальный портрет одинокого родителя / Г.Л. Воронин, А.Л. Янак // *Женщина в российском обществе*. – 2018. – № 1 (86). – С. 53–66.